
COP26: Implications for Energy Networks

1. COP26 and why it was important ¹

Conference of the Parties (COP) is arguably one of the most important international conferences, bringing together governments and policymakers from across the globe to deliberate on matters concerning global climate. This conference was borne out of the mandate of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC)², to ensure that atmospheric greenhouse gas concentrations are kept below harmful levels in order to reduce global warming.

Since the first COP meeting in 1995, member countries have convened annually to agree guidelines that could be adopted by all member countries in order to commit to abating the global threat of climate change. It took nearly twenty years for nations to sign the Paris Agreement³ at COP21 (2015). The Paris Agreement took on the mandate to hold to account all its signatories on the pledges (referred to as the Nationally Determined Contributions – NDCs) they have made to reduce their greenhouse gas emissions, and commit to working together to limit global warming to below 2°C or, more ambitiously, below 1.5°C compared to pre-industrial levels.

Figure 1 shows the Climate Action Tracker thermometer, an independent scientific tool that tracks government climate action and measures it against the globally agreed Paris Agreement targets, where it is predicted that the current pledges made by individual countries would only be able to limit global temperature rise to 2.4°C by 2100, which is far beyond the limit set in the Paris Agreement. COP26 was thus a consequential meeting with the task of re-evaluating the plans made in the Paris Agreement, rescuing the planet from the looming climate change crisis.

¹ <https://www.nhm.ac.uk/discover/news/2021/october/cop26-explained.html>

² <https://unfccc.int/about-us/about-the-secretariat>

³ <https://www.un.org/en/climatechange/paris-agreement>

Figure 1: Climate Action Tracker thermometer⁴ predictions on global warming by 2100. The temperatures on the CAT thermometer are ‘median’ warming estimates in 2100. This means that there is a 50% chance that the calculated temperature would be exceeded if the given emissions pathway is followed. For example, there is a 50% chance that warming associated with our pledges and targets scenario exceeds 2.1°C in 2100.

2. Key outcomes of the COP26 meeting^{5,6,7,8,9}

In the context of the renewed urgency brought about by the fast-rising global temperatures, COP26 was a meeting at which countries of the world were faced with the pressure to arrive at a concrete agreement that helps put into action all tools required to move toward a net-zero global economy by 2050. Two key outcomes that capture the essence of this urgency are the Glasgow Climate Pact, as well as the finalization of the Paris Rulebook. The latter delivers a framework that specifies clearer guidelines to be followed by all countries that have pledged to do their part in achieving a zero-carbon future which the Paris Agreement aspires for.

The following were the notable outcomes of the COP26 meeting:

2.1. *Emphasis on upholding the 1.5°C limit on the rise of global temperatures*

With the current reading of the global warming thermometer currently at 1.2°C, there is reason to be concerned. The Climate Action Tracker has also revealed that the

⁴ <https://climateactiontracker.org/global/cat-thermometer/>

⁵ <https://www.carbonbrief.org/cop26-key-outcomes-agreed-at-the-un-climate-talks-in-glasgow>

⁶ <https://ukcop26.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/COP26-Presidency-Outcomes-The-Climate-Pact.pdf>

⁷ https://ecologi.com/articles/blog/what-was-agreed-at-cop26?gclid=CjwKCAiA24SPBhB0EiwAjBgkhlNyJWCdf0VAyZA0Ktd0U4r3f-qXiPSiB1sV2DR_ilno1MR7LU8s2RoCRcwQAvD_BwE

⁸ <https://www.nhm.ac.uk/discover/news/2021/october/COP26-live-blog.html>

⁹ <https://www.chathamhouse.org/sites/default/files/2021-11/2021-11-15-COP26-what-happened-summary-Aberg-et-al.pdf>

current NDCs alone would lead to disastrous global warming (2.4°C by 2100). There was therefore a strong consensus to limit global temperature increases to 1.5°C, instead of the more conservative global warming limit of 2°C. This is in recognition of the pace at which the climate change crisis is escalating and acknowledging that the plans to limit global warming ought to be all the more ambitious in light of the progress made to date.

2.2. *Intensified requirements for the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions*

Countries have agreed that the 1.5°C ambition be pursued, though progress at present is slow. Given this, countries are expected to upscale their NDCs and translate them into rapidly actionable plans to cut down on the greenhouse gas emissions in order to achieve the 1.5°C goal. The NDCs will now be evaluated annually instead of 5-yearly and in accordance with the rigorous guidelines set out in the Paris Rulebook.

2.3. *Accelerating the phase-down of coal power and phase-out of inefficient fossil fuel subsidies*

Though there is now a common urgency to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, there was no clear mention in the Paris Agreement on how that may be achieved. An agreement was thus entered into at the COP26 meeting to phase down coal power and also to phase out inefficient fossil fuel subsidies. Despite the contention around the precise language used in the wording of the agreement (with some nations preferring the use of *phase-out* to *phase-down* in reference to coal power), there was generally a positive feeling that the decision to specify what must happen to coal power and the subsidies on fossil fuels was, nonetheless, a step in the right direction. In fact, it is expected that at least 40% of existing coal-fired power generation facilities must be decommissioned by 2030 and that no new such facilities shall be built. Countries were also requested to drastically cut down on methane emissions within the current decade.

2.4. *Reviving the climate finance and adaptation plan*

In 2009, industrialized countries had pledged to provide an annual sum of at least US\$100 billion to developing countries between 2015 and 2020 to assist these nations with their greenhouse gas emissions mitigation programmes and for financing adaptation plans to cope with natural disasters that stem from the climate change crisis. Until 2019, however, this pledge was still close to US\$20 billion short of coming to fruition. A recommitment was thus made at COP26 to deliver on this pledge by 2025. These funds will go toward financing greenhouse gas emissions mitigation programmes such as renewable energy schemes and green technology development, as well as disaster preparedness and management programmes such as flood prevention and drought relief.

2.5. *Regulation for carbon markets*

Long overdue carbon market rules were agreed at COP26. These rules are aimed at creating a regulated market for trading carbon credits. Since the adoption of the Kyoto

Protocol¹⁰ (1997), the trading of carbon credits has been used by a number of countries as a tool to limit their greenhouse gas emissions. Countries did this through purchasing offset carbon credits that represent an equivalent of greenhouse gas emissions reduction by other countries in order to meet their climate targets. In the absence of a regulatory framework to manage the trading of carbon credits, there has been an issue of double-counting of carbon credits by the selling countries and the buying countries. There is now a set of new rules to regulate the trading of carbon credits, which is hoped to address all the issues that had affected the trading of carbon credits.

Since these rules are now tailored for the Paris Agreement, the carbon market rules also provide a framework within which the carbon credits traded under the Kyoto Protocol may be carried over to the Paris Agreement.

In spite of the questions that continue to linger around the regulation of the carbon markets, what is certain is that there will be increased utilization of carbon credits exchange in the intensified race toward achieving the global warming reduction goals. This means that we will see enormous scores of funds in form of carbon credits being directed toward projects relating to developing new green energy resources such as solar, tidal, wind, and green hydrogen resources, and also toward carbon capture projects such as natural vegetation restoration (afforestation).

3. What do the outcomes of COP26 mean for energy networks?^{11,12}

There is an international consensus that now is the time to act with renewed efforts toward alleviating the impact of climate change and ensure that the factors contributing to the climate change crisis are abated. Moreover, there is no dispute that energy networks greenhouse gas emissions contribute to the rise in global temperatures. Many outcomes of COP26 have far-reaching implications on the pace that energy networks modernization will need to adopt. These specific outcomes include the intensified drive to limit global temperatures below 1.5°C, the phasing down of coal-based power and the phase-out of fossil fuel subsidies, climate change and adaptation finances, and carbon markets incentives.

The following is some reflection on what the key outcomes of COP26 mean for the future of global energy networks:

- *The agreement to phase-down the use of coal power and the phase-out of fossil fuel subsidies* means that the amount of electrical power that is currently sourced from coal-fired power generation facilities will be significantly reduced. Prospecting for oil and gas resources will also be curtailed as subsidies begin to diminish. These changes are expected to materialize within this decade, with fossil fuels production and usage expected to have slowed down or ceased by 2030. These changes are probably happening at a much faster pace than we had initially anticipated prior to

¹⁰ https://unfccc.int/kyoto_protocol

¹¹ <https://www.nationalgrideso.com/news/top-five-takeaways-cop26>

¹² <https://www.pinsentmasons.com/out-law/analysis/what-next-energy-transition-cop26>

COP26. Therefore, in place of fossil fuels, energy needs will need to be met via cleaner alternative energy resources such as solar, tidal, and wind renewable energy, as well as green hydrogen. This means that energy services such as space-heating technologies and motor vehicles (including other forms of transport) that use fossil-based fuels will either need to be electrified or adopt the use of green hydrogen. All of these changes will introduce new energy demand onto the energy system.

- The *re-invigorated plan to provide financial resources to developing countries to assist them with their greenhouse gas emissions mitigation programmes* will spur up accelerated adoption of low-carbon energy in these countries. While this could help developing nations achieve their NDC targets quicker, adopting low-carbon energy at scale will depend on the absorption capacity of the energy networks in these nations. This challenge is not unique to developing nations; it is a global challenge – the difference, however, is that it will be a lot more challenging for developing nations due to the shortage of financial resources required to upgrade the energy networks infrastructure.
- It is hoped that the *emergence of refined carbon trading regulations* will help improve transparency, leading to increased utilization of carbon trading.

Though all agreements made during COP26 would help to address the climate crisis, we are confronted with the practicalities of how these plans could be realized. From the perspective of energy networks, it means that the energy networks will need to adapt to the new energy resources and applications by essentially undergoing a rapid transformation that enables these networks to serve as a well-suited conduit for delivering energy to customers. The important function of energy networks is to deliver energy to customers in a reliable, sustainable, and cost-effective manner.

The introduction of low-carbon energy onto the energy networks largely includes the adoption of variable, non-dispatchable renewable energy such as solar, tidal, and wind energy, whether integrating these onto the mega energy network or in stand-alone/islanded mode. The intermittent nature of these energy sources introduces a reliability problem on the energy networks. These new sources of energy are not always available at the times when they are most needed. This means that for energy networks to continue delivering energy to customers in a reliable, sustainable, and cost-effective manner, two main things need to happen: firstly, the capability to store energy at times of excess generation and low demand and dispatch it when demand rises during times of low generation, and secondly, customers must become adaptive and flexible in their energy use patterns. Therefore, energy networks designers and operators must adopt revised approaches to ensure that the energy networks will continue to deliver reliability and flexibility in their core function of acting as a conduit for energy to customers.

The electrification of motor vehicles has already given rise to the introduction of electric vehicles onto the energy networks. This is a new load that must be served by the energy networks. The charging of these vehicles, as one can imagine, will be very stochastic in nature. Combining the stochasticity of the charging of these vehicles with the intermittency in energy generation gives rise to a chaotic reality. A lot of charging infrastructures are increasingly being

added onto the energy networks to cater to the rising number of electric vehicles. In order to build flexibility into the operation of energy networks and to take advantage of the batteries fitted on electric vehicles, the charging facilities are being built with the capability for electric vehicles to discharge energy into the energy network when necessary. This means that the stochasticity issue will not only exist on the demand for energy by electric vehicles, but also on the reverse injection of power from electric vehicles through what is called vehicle to grid (V2G) technology. All of this requires the energy networks to adopt a flexible way of operation to cater to the stochastic nature of new energy appliances. Careful coordination of energy exchange will be crucial, and aspects of cyber security will also be valid concerns in operating such a digitally connected energy network.

The heating sector is also undergoing a rapid revolution of decarbonization. It is believed that green hydrogen will act as cushion that will allow us to transition from fossil-based oil and gas dependency into an era of low-carbon heating. Existing heating fuel will most likely adopt green hydrogen in place of methane-based gas heating. What this means for energy networks is that the existing gas networks will need to undergo re-designing or some sort of adaptation in order to be able to transport green hydrogen reliably and securely. Hydrogen is considered cleaner than methane since burning hydrogen only produces water as a by-product, whereas burning methane produces carbon dioxide and water. In this sense, green hydrogen, which is produced by splitting water via electrolysis using renewable energy, is the most promising route for heating.

4. Concluding Remarks

The next decades will see an energy network revolution as a result of the drive for decarbonization targets outlined during COP26. The goal is to achieve a net-zero global economy by 2050, and eventually, a zero-carbon global economy by 2100. The role of the energy sector in bringing about this reality is immense. Fossil fuels will be replaced with low-carbon energy resources such as solar, tidal, and wind energy resources, motor vehicles will be electrified, and heating will adopt green hydrogen as a form of fuel. All of this requires energy networks that are capable to deliver energy to customers in a reliable, sustainable, and cost-effective manner while navigating the complexity that arises from the integration of the variable energy sources (solar, tidal, and wind energy) and smart energy applications (V2G, demand-side response (DSR)). This capability will inevitably require flexibility in adapting to the decentralized/dispersed intermittent energy sources and the stochastic nature of energy demand. Flexibility will in turn rely on digital technology (IoT, AI, etc.) to ensure that there is a secure and reliable exchange of control signals between supply and demand points to coordinate generation and the use of energy in an efficient and sustainable way. Energy networks will need to be holistic in nature, coordinating the supply and consumption of energy in a multi-vector (electricity, transport, heating) environment.

In embracing this global drive for decarbonization, a global approach is necessary. No one will be safe if the rise in global temperatures continues unabated. More than ever, the energy networks infrastructures will need to undergo rapid transformation at a greater rate and scale than the transformation required in low-carbon energy production. Energy networks are a conduit for the dispersed low-carbon energy through which energy must be delivered to

customers. The COP meetings often only focus on decarbonizing energy sources, but there is perhaps not enough emphasis on the facilities required to deliver that energy to customers.

The race is on. The task is decarbonization. It is a global task. Collaboration is essential in accomplishing this task.